

You could choose a brighter ending song. These three are too similar in tempo & rhythm and might sound a little monotonous.

Song Recital
(Tenor and Piano)

- Come again John Dowland
(1562-1626)
- Flow not so fast, ye fountains Philip Rossèter
(1568-1623)
- When Laura smiles Tobias Hume
(1569-1645)
- Fain would I change that note

- Sehnsucht Carl Friedrich Zelter
(1758-1832)
- Wo gehts Liebchen ?
- Es klingt in der Luft, op.13, no.2 Robert Franz
(1815-1892)
- Waldeggespräch, op.5, no.4 Adolf Jensen
(1837-1918)
- Frühlingsnacht, op.1, no.6
- Margret am Tore, op.33, no.5

Rather short first part

INTERMISSION

- Fetes Galantes (I) Claude Debussy
(1862-1918)
 - En sourdine
 - Fantoches
 - Clair de lune
- Six Elizabethan Songs Dominick Argento
(1927-)
 - Spring
 - Sleep
 - Winter
 - Dirge
 - Diaphenia
 - Hymn

The entire programme is short. An adult vocal group in the first part would enhance it.

I do not know all of these songs, but it seems an interesting group.

PROGRAM BUILDING

Basic program

1st group: Earlier period - not too long
pleasant mood - (1st song should be easy)

2nd group:

3rd group:

INTERMISSION

2 { 1st group: (special group)

2nd group: (folk songs, contemporary, etc.)

Things to remember

BEGIN AND END BRILLIANTLY

Stamina - be sure you can get through

CYCLES - build around them

CYCLES which require full evening -

2 Schubert

Brahms - Magalone

Wolf - Italian - (man + woman)

Hindemith - Marie Celeste

VARIETY - Something for everyone - Right repertoire for the particular group

PLAN KEYS + TEMPI carefully - don't have 2 songs together in same key

DON'T MIX COMPOSERS IN A GROUP (EX: 1ST GROUP)

DON'T MIX LANGUAGES IN A GROUP, OR SACRED/SECULAR

SUBJECT GROUPS = Serenade, folk song settings

NO ARIAS

Rules for Vocal Accompaniment · G. Koldofsky

Procedure for learning a song

1. Read the poem - translation
2. Read original for word by word meaning
3. Recite as actor - in original lang. and translation
4. Recite in rhythm
5. play vocal line
6. play vocal line + bass line of acc.

always - play with the vowel

how to improve your accompanying immediately -
MORE BASS!

SONG LITERATURE

1st semester - Italian, English, German

2nd - French, Russian, Spanish, American

Middle ages - Renaissance - Stevens, 38-40, 54-62, 96-104

Schöne Müllerin - Gerald Moore

Books for reference Lotte Lehman

Fischer-Diskau

A. Craig Bell

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arm-finger-wrist - Body → different colors

more line consciousness

Sad, heavy - slow attack

more horizontal - less vertical

watch out for soft pedal - only for effects

BEETHOVEN - structural points need articulation

leaping down - time will help

(Bb maj chord - 2nd finger ^(on D) in further)

no accents where not needed

Lahn + Weihen

↓

major-minor

crisper
attack +
release

Der Wanderer

don't break line
in 2

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Beethoven - more into keys for p - control, clarity

dynamic contrasts more pronounced

practice: l.h legato along with trills

Schubert SOUND - close to Mozart (Faure thrown in)

curved fingers - clear articulation - melody as in Debussy

DIE ZWERG. angle towards the thumb - bring out melody (fingering)

projection - equivalent of stage make up "LARGER THAN LIFE"